

DEVELOPMENT OF THE ABILITY OF TABLE TENNIS PLAYERS TO MAINTAIN BODY BALANCE AT THE INITIAL PREPARATORY STAGE

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Annotation: This article reveals the role of the body balance maintenance function in the process of initial training in table tennis. It has been shown that a poorly formed statokinetic reaction slows down the pace of mastering table tennis skills.

Keywords: table tennis, initial training, balance, stability, statokinetics, vestibular analyzer.

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрывается роль функции поддержания равновесия тела в процессе начальной подготовки в настольном теннисе. Было показано, что слабо сформированная статокинетическая реакция замедляет темп овладения навыками настольного тенниса.

Ключевые слова: настольный теннис, начальное обучения, равновесие, устойчивость, статокинетика, вестибулярный анализатор.

Relevance of the topic: during the observation of the training carried out in the groups of beginner sports training, this is what is noticeable that most trainers give priority to the formation of technical and tactical skills, which is the main focus in the training process. Leading specialist scientists in the field, however, emphasize the need to develop physical qualities in a proportional order, first of all, in order to intensively master the technical and tactical methods inherent in the chosen sport. But it is also known that while the coordinate of the character (accuracy as well) is controlled according to physiological laws on the basis of the integral activity of almost all analyzers, its perfection (stability) can be ensured by the center-vestibular analyzer, which controls the balancing function. Therefore, regular formation of the function of

maintaining the static and dynamic balance of the body in children who have "stepped" on Table Tennis makes it possible to intensively master the skills of Table tennis, which are taught.

Today, a number of mistakes and shortcomings can be seen in the process of performing technical and tactical actions and physical exercises in the initial preparatory classes of children who have already started playing the sport of Table tennis. This is evidenced by the weak development of the functional capacity of the vestibular analyzer in athletes who have started playing table tennis.

It is known that during long training and competition games in table tennis, table tennis players often perform fast movements performed in extremely sharply changing directions – maximum acceleration to short intervals and elements such as sharp stops, turns-turns, bends-turns, bends-turns as an integral load, affecting primarily the control function of the vestibular analyzer, causing a violation of balance. This causes athletes to get tired quickly during training and misappropriation of the loadings given. To avoid such frustrating processes, to properly master the sports techniques and loadings of table tennis players, to achieve victory in sports competitions by achieving high sports results, requires the coach to properly organize sports training, distribute the loadings based on the physical capabilities of those involved, and as a result, the opportunity is created by table tennis players at the initial.

Conclusion. From the above data, it can be recognized that table tennis players who are engaged in the initial preparatory stage will have limited chances of maintaining a static and dynamic balance due to the weak formation of the neural receptor of the vestibular analyzer. Such a statokinetic and vestibulosomatic reaction had a negative effect on the accuracy of the ball targeting coordination Hamda. Therefore, it is of important practical importance to find a targeted bleach for the function of static and dynamic balancing from childhood in order to ensure the effectiveness of the initial training in table tennis, especially the Coordination of movement and the formation of its accuracy.

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